

Under the Shadow of God's Wings

Tessy Sebastian SH

Institute Mater Dei, Goa

We are living in a world of grave crisis because of the Coronavirus. As disciples of Jesus, how do we respond to this situation? In the Old Testament, many of the Psalms speak of the trust of the people who are caught up in difficult situations. Psalm 91 is one of these special Psalms in which the people have repeatedly turned to God in times of sickness, loneliness, and trouble. It has been committed to heart by thousands of people, and millions have turned to it with thankfulness in the midst of life's calamities. In the words of Athanasius to Marcellinus, "If you desire to establish yourself and others in devotion, to know what confidence is to be reposed in God, and what makes the mind fearless, you will praise God by reciting the ninetieth (ninety-first) Psalm". At this time of global pandemic with the novel coronavirus COVID-19, this Psalm speaks of God's power, presence, intentions, and protection against fear. Psalm 91 is ordinarily classified as a Psalm of Confidence or Trust.

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The Message of the Psalm

Psalm 91 is a classic on the sure providence of God as the citadel of faith. The first verse of Psalm 91 is a thematic statement, expressing what the remainder of the Psalm will be about: "You who dwells in the shelter of the Most High/ Who abide in the shadow of the Almighty" (v.1)

When the Psalmist makes this statement he immediately breaks in to confess his own faith before commending it to us: “I will say of the LORD, ‘He is *my* refuge and *my* fortress, *my* God, in whom I trust’ ” (v. 2). This poses a question to each one of us: Is the God of the Bible my refuge and my fortress in times of trouble? The Psalmist identifies God as his shelter, shadow, refuge, and fortress on whom one can trust.

In God’s covenants with Israel, God promises abundance as the nation is faithful. When they committed themselves to God, He gave success in their purpose of inhabiting the Promised Land. As they trusted, no pestilence would keep the Israelite army from defeating its enemies and from becoming the nation God promised. The language and imagery of Psalm 91 are open-ended enough to be relevant and powerful in many situations. Indeed, Psalm 91 has served throughout the centuries and continues to serve as a source of encouragement and strength for the people of God. The Psalm seems to be the work of a teacher who seeks to nurture the trust of

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the faithful by encouraging each of them to take the LORD as their refuge from all the troubles of life.

Psalm 91 assures Israel of the safety from peril for those who make the temple of God their

habitual resort (91:1-2). Then, in a direct address, the Psalmist exhorts them not to fear the pestilence which is destroying multitudes on every side (v. 5-7). He also emphasizes that God will keep them safely in the hands of guardian angels (v. 9. 11-13). Finally, he speaks in the name of God, assuring the promise of God’s deliverance, protection and His everlasting presence for those who love and know Him (v. 14-16). The life of the faithful in Israel was set in an environment of threatening dangers. In this Psalm, the word “pestilence” is described in several terms: ‘the terror of the night’ (v.5a); the ‘arrow that flies by day’(v.5b); the ‘destruction

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that wastes at noonday’(v.6). Thus, one has to face multiple currents and structural threats to one’s life like crisis situation of “danger from enemies/persecution” and “sickness/death”. When the Psalmist speaks of ‘pestilence’ he may have in mind an evil spell. This vocabulary and its frequency in the Psalms bring out the important role of trust in coping with the anxieties that beset their life. The Psalmist is not unaware of dangers, but any fear of adversaries is far outweighed by his confidence in the security that derives from God.

God Protects Us

The following verses describe the protection of God from many dangers (vv. 3-13). Yet in all of these situations, one has a shelter with God — his faithfulness will be their shield and rampart (v. 4b). The wing of the cherubim covered the space over the cover of the Ark which God had chosen to make his throne. A person may trust in God, commit himself and his way to God, and know he is forever secure in God’s hand. The word “Refuge” used as a metaphor for God’s care and protection

is a pervasive theme in the Psalter. In its liturgical context, it means to look to the LORD for security from threatening dangers. Basically, the theme of the Psalm can be summed up in one word: “security.” That security is found through faith in God. All such threatening forces are robbed of their destructive power because the worshipper is encircled within God’s protecting power. The theme of the Psalm, as noted, is God’s

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protective care of one who is committed to him. The essence of the security of which the Psalm speaks lies in a continuing relationship with God. God will save the trusting soul from two kinds of dangers: first, the subtle snare of enemies, described as the trap a fowler used to catch birds, and second, death by disease or pestilence. He will save us from the corona pandemic in ways unknown to us. But surely, he will protect us.

Conclusion

God is our refuge, comfort, and shade amidst pandemic. Described as a protection for His people, God's comfort is a wing of security amidst this world's uncertainties and suffering. Trusting in God grants no exemption from the life-threatening and destructive forces which are part of human experience, but it deprives them of their sting and enables them to face without fear. Our focus should not be on fear and uncertainty but in God alone, even in circumstances of diseases and troubles. In short, this Psalm urges us to be the beacons of hope and to trust and cling to God in all the circumstances of our life.